

Article

Efficiency Analysis of NIST-Standardized Post-Quantum Cryptographic Algorithms for Digital Signatures in Various Environments

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Abstract: The advent of quantum computing presents a significant threat to the security of asymmetric cryptographic algorithms, necessitating the adoption of new cryptographic mechanisms resilient to quantum-based attacks. This need is particularly critical for applications that rely exclusively on public-key cryptography, such as digital signatures. This paper presents a comprehensive analysis of the performance of various post-quantum cryptographic algorithms, focusing specifically on NIST-standardized digital signature algorithms—SPHINCS+ and Dilithium—and their practical implementations. The study evaluates these algorithms across different programming languages to identify optimal environments for diverse applications. Comparative analyses with the widely used RSA algorithm reveal that the computational cost of adopting post-quantum cryptographic systems is relatively low. Notably, some post-quantum algorithms demonstrate performance advantages over classical RSA in specific scenarios.

Keywords: post-quantum cryptography; digital signature; cybersecurity; data integrity

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1. Introduction

In today's rapidly evolving digital world, securing data is more crucial than ever. With almost all aspects of everyday life taking place in a virtual landscape, data confidentiality is paramount. Many measures to safeguard sensitive information and prevent eavesdropping have been developed; however, with advancements in security also come advancements in methods to break it. Currently used asymmetric cryptographic algorithms rely on the difficulty of solving complex mathematical problems, taking present-day computers vast amounts of time, making this approach useless for brute-force attacks. Although these algorithms are still secure, theoretical measures of breaking them have already been developed [1], lacking only powerful enough quantum computers. With ever present breakthroughs in the quantum computing field, we are closer and closer to currently used asymmetric ciphers not being able to provide necessary security.

Although current cryptographic algorithms such as RSA (Rivest–Shamir–Adleman) [2] remain computationally secure, it is still possible to store encrypted data and use means of decrypting them when they become available. Because of this, the transition to quantum-secure cryptography as soon as possible is paramount. There are two ways of providing quantum-secure means of data transfer: quantum and post-quantum algorithms. The first relies on principles of quantum physics to ensure data security by eliminating the possibility of eavesdropping, as an act of observing destroys quantum state. The downside of this approach is the requirement of dedicated quantum channels (e.g., fiber optic cables). Another challenge is the decoherence of quantum bits sent this way. One of the principles

with respect to guaranteeing security—the inability to copy an unknown quantum state—severely limits the distance of data transfer. As of now, no quantum repeaters have been built, meaning quantum networks require stations decrypting and encrypting messages along the way called trusted nodes, providing more points of attack. The second approach to protect data against quantum attacks is post-quantum cryptography. Such algorithms use complex mathematical problems that are also considered hard for quantum computers. However, these algorithms are usable with classical computers and already existing network infrastructure [3]. Taking this into consideration, post-quantum algorithms are more affordable and easier to implement in practice.

When creating networks using new technologies, it is crucial to fully understand all of their aspects, with one of the most important being security [4]. To anticipate possible quantum attacks, the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) has developed a list of quantum-secure algorithms. They have been thoroughly tested, and recently, a list of three finalized post-quantum encryption algorithm families has been released [5]. Many industries, including energy, finance, healthcare, and government, will soon be required to adopt post-quantum algorithms to comply with new legal standards and regulations to provide the highest degree of security for their clients. In fact, several countries are already setting legal frameworks for a secure transition to post-quantum cryptography. Regulations like the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) emphasize the need for ongoing risk assessments, which now include anticipating future quantum-based threats. Moreover, compliance with security protocols that ensure that data remain encrypted and protected in a post-quantum world will likely become mandatory for organizations handling sensitive information, including critical infrastructure sectors. This evolving landscape means that legal requirements will drive the adoption of post-quantum cryptographic standards, ensuring resilience against the next generation of cyber threats.

This paper focuses on measuring the performance of various post-quantum algorithms, comparing their efficiency and scalability across different programming languages, with particular attention to digital signatures—critical components of secure communication in distributed environments. Digital signatures form the foundation for secure communication, software integrity, and transactions by verifying the identity of the message's author and making such a requirement essential for maintaining trust across online platforms. As quantum computing poses a growing threat, securing these signatures with quantum-resistant methods becomes paramount. While advancements in hardware will certainly improve the speed and performance of post-quantum algorithms over time, the most crucial factor lies in the mathematical mechanism used by the algorithm. Approaches implementing lattice-based cryptography [6] may offer better performance on classical hardware, while others, like hash-based cryptography [7], can be more resource-intensive. This article considers the time efficiency of various post-quantum digital signature algorithms, providing examples and performance benchmarks to evaluate their viability for real-world applications—including smart grids and automotive applications—to ensure current and future security needs.

This paper is structured as follows. Section 2 summarizes the basics of modern cryptography. Section 3 discusses various approaches and algorithms used in post-quantum cryptography. Testing environment and tools used have been discussed in Section 4. Section 5 focuses on analyzing the performance. Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. Modern Cryptography

Data security is becoming increasingly important as the world becomes more digital. One way of ensuring data confidentiality is through symmetric algorithms such as the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) [8]. First, a digital key is generated and used to

encrypt the data. Because of operations being simple and computationally efficient, large quantities of information can be quickly encrypted. Then, the same key is used to perform the reverse operation, hence the name 'symmetric'. This approach performs well in systems where the key is known for both parties, like disk encryption. However, it encounters a major challenge—secure key distribution. If the key is intercepted during transmission, the system's security is compromised. In large, decentralized systems like the internet, managing and sharing keys with every new user without exposing them to potential attacks becomes very difficult. As a result, symmetric algorithms alone are not practical for scenarios involving multiple users or dynamic networks. To solve this, asymmetric cryptography is used in practice, which allows for secure key exchange without the need to share a secret key directly.

Asymmetric cryptography utilizes a pair of keys for each user—public and private. This approach removes the necessity of transporting a confidential key through public channels, making it more feasible for communication over the internet. Examples of asymmetric cryptography include RSA, which relies on computational the difficulty of factoring large numbers, and elliptic curve cryptography (ECC) [9], which depends on the hardness of elliptic curve discrete logarithm problems. Both techniques ensure that, even if the public key is known to an attacker, deriving the private key remains computationally infeasible. One of the main strengths of this encryption scheme is the distribution of public keys. They can be freely shared without compromising security, allowing for establishing private and secure communication channels between new users. This approach greatly reduces the number of keys needed for a functional network, rendering it particularly useful for systems with large amount of users needing data confidentiality—such as online banking.

One of the most prominent applications of asymmetric cryptography is the digital signature scheme, allowing for data authenticity and preventing the modification of messages. As asymmetric cryptography is computationally inefficient—for example, RSA involves raising numbers to large powers, which is computationally expensive—making the input message as small as possible is a crucial step. To achieve this, a hashing function is implemented, reducing the whole message to a short fixed number of bytes called hash. The computed hash is then encrypted using the private key and sent to the other user alongside the original data. To verify the digest, the recipient has to calculate the hash of the original data and compare it with the hash decrypted using the public key of sender. Any differences between the decrypted and calculated hash indicate data tampering and mean that the signature is not correct.

Throughout the years, the RSA algorithm became the industry standard and is still widely used today. Of course, key lengths used 30 years ago can be broken today using a personal computer in a few hours. Due to its variable key length, the key size can be easily increased as computers approach the computational power required to break the encryption. There is, however, an issue with this approach—data sent using public channels can easily be stored and later decrypted, both by more powerful classical computers or a theoretical, not yet developed quantum computer with enough qubits.

Recent developments in the field of quantum physics brought a new way of securing communication: quantum key distribution [10,11]. This approach allows users to establish secure symmetric keys and provide resistance to attacks involving quantum computers. Using the principles of quantum states, it is possible to establish a new, symmetrical key between two parties, without the possibility of eavesdropping, as an act of measuring a quantum particle destroys a quantum state. Usually, the polarization of photons is used to transmit data in the quantum channel. Then, users verify if any eavesdropper is present by exchanging additional data via the public channel. Random bits of the established string of bits are compared—if they match, no eavesdropping has occurred. However if

the error rate exceeds certain threshold, users conclude that the key exchange has been compromised. The primary challenge with this approach is decoherence, as the quantum state deteriorates over time and distance. The main principle guaranteeing security of this system, the inability to copy the quantum state, severely limits the distance between the user. Academic quantum networks have already been built [12], but without the technology of quantum repeaters, their usage will be severely limited. Another issue is that quantum key distribution networks (QKDNs) can hardly guarantee the theoretical security of quantum key distribution (QKD) algorithms [13]. Therefore, it seems that the only alternative to quantum-secure solutions currently available is post-quantum cryptography.

3. Post-Quantum Cryptography

Organizations like the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) issued an open call [14] for the submission of post-quantum cryptographic algorithms. Firstly, NIST released a draft of minimum acceptability requirements and evaluation criteria. Comments were received, and a summary of the changes made to the algorithms has been publicly posted [15]. Algorithms that have satisfied the minimum acceptability requirements of a “complete and proper” submission were chosen as the finalists. The goal was to identify algorithms that would be quantum-resistant, practical, and secure against attacks (including quantum-based ones). They were evaluated based on several key factors, mainly their security, performance, flexibility, and key and signature size. They represented a wide range of mathematical techniques briefly summarized below:

- **Lattice-based cryptography** [6]—it relies on the hardness of solving problems in high-dimensional lattices, which are grids of points in multidimensional space. The most common problems include learning with errors (LWEs) [16] and the shortest vector problem (SVP). The former revolves around the difficulty of finding original lattice points with given noisy data, and the latter rests on the difficulty of finding the closest point using given vectors as the basis of said lattice.
- **Code-based cryptography** [17]—it leverages the difficulty of decoding random error-correcting codes. Given the scrambled codeword, it is extremely difficult to find the original message unless the structure of the underlying code (private key) is known. Solving general decoding problems remains computationally difficult even for quantum computers, rendering this approach a potential candidate. The main drawbacks of code-based cryptography are large public and private keys, as they are sizable matrices extending to hundreds of kilobits.
- **Hash-based cryptography** [7]—it uses the security of one-way hash functions to create digital signatures. The most popular example, SPHINCS+, relies on Merkle trees and one-time signatures. The simplicity and proven security of hashing functions make them a solid candidate for post-quantum cryptography. However, it is used primarily for signatures, and their sizes can grow large, especially for stateless hash-based schemes.

Another technique is Isogeny-based cryptography, which relies on the difficulty of finding isogenies between elliptic curves, but its security was proven to be not sufficient. In 2022, an efficient attack on the Supersingular Isogeny Key Exchange (SIKE) scheme was performed, resulting in breaking the security of this approach [18].

Numbers of algorithms representing the mentioned cryptographic methods were presented, of which only a few were deemed secure and robust enough for widespread implementation. Recently, the NIST released a list of approved algorithms [5] characterized below:

- **CRYSTALS-Kyber** [19] is a key encapsulation mechanism (KEM) relying on lattice cryptography and learning with errors problem. It allows user to generate and send a secret key to another user securely. Kyber’s lattice structure offers high security,

efficiency, and relatively compact key sizes, making it a strong candidate for real-world applications like secure communication protocols. As this algorithm is not a part of the public-key encryption scheme, it will not be a focus of this paper.

- **CRYSTALS-Dilithium** [20] is a digital signature algorithm that also uses lattice-based cryptography, relying on the learning with errors and learning with rounding problems. It offers robust security with reasonable signature and key sizes, and it is notable for its efficiency in performing these tasks. Dilithium's solid performance has contributed to its selection as a leading post-quantum signature scheme.
- **SPHINCS+** [21] is a hash-based digital signature scheme that builds on the security of cryptographic hash functions, such as SHA-256. Being designed as a stateless signature scheme means it does not rely on maintaining the internal state between signature generations. It uses Merkle trees and one-time signature schemes to ensure security and quantum resistance.

Although the NIST has already released a list of approved algorithms, new ones are still being developed as a part of round-4 submissions [22].

4. Test Environment and Methodology

The comprehensive performance testing of classical and post-quantum cryptographic algorithms was performed using a containerized environment, ensuring consistent measurements. The tools used for implementation and visualization are described below:

- **Liboqs library**—the liboqs (Open Quantum Safe project) [23] library served as a critical component in this benchmarking study, providing highly optimized implementations of discussed post-quantum algorithms. The extensive documentation and high variety of example scripts and test cases allow for effortless implementation in a wide variety of projects and applications. In addition to the core C library, liboqs provides official wrappers allowing for development in alternative languages, of which C++, Python, and Golang were chosen. These wrappers retained the high performance of the original C library while offering interfaces that are idiomatic and natural for developers in each language.
- **Docker**—this solution was selected as the test platform to create isolated, reproducible testing environments for each language. A separate Docker container was built for each wrapper, utilizing sample Dockerfiles sourced from official repositories. This approach allowed us to test post-quantum algorithms with minimum overhead from other applications.
- **Python**—a Python command-line interface (CLI) application was used for automatic test orchestration and data collection across many iterations and docker containers. Python scripts also managed post-processing and data visualization, allowing for the creation of detailed performance graphs.

The primary objective of this research is to assess the performance of post-quantum algorithms approved by the NIST for digital signatures. The efficiency of these algorithms—designed to be resilient against quantum attacks—was compared across multiple programming languages. To achieve this goal, the times of key generation, as well as the signing and verification processes, were measured for each algorithm across 100 iterations. Selection of the tested algorithms was guided by the liboqs method for retrieving a list of supported signature (SIG) algorithms, leading to slight variations for different languages. To evaluate their scalability, identical tests were performed across four file sizes: 1 KB, 1 MB, 50 MB, and 1 GB. The content of these files was randomly generated and used as input for each iteration to avoid any variations caused by differences in input files. Proper variability representation when performing measurements across many iterations is essential. This

study utilized the standard error of the mean (SEM) for each graph to provide quantifiable indication of this variation.

To provide an equivalent environment for each test case, the Docker containers used parameters presented in Table 1. They were run sequentially to further reduce any possibility of cross-contamination of the results. Throughout that time, measurements were performed by the scripts running in the Docker containers to eliminate any time errors caused by communication between the container and host PC and later returned in the JSON format.

Table 1. Docker container specifications.

Parameter	Details
Container operating system	Ubuntu 24.04 LTS
Docker memory limit	8 GB
Number of processors	1
Host CPU	AMD Ryzen 5 5600X 3.7 GHz
Disk type	NVMe

It is worth mentioning that due to the need for loading data and instructions, the key generation time for a first algorithm during each iteration was noticeably longer. This disparity was especially noticeable for the low-level languages, while higher-level languages were less affected. This led to instances where Python wrapper vastly outperformed the original C library, as showcased in Figure 1. To eliminate the issue, 10 ‘warmup’ iterations were added before the time measurement phase for each algorithm.

Figure 1. Performance measurement without ‘warmup’ phase (Dilithium2 algorithm), showcasing significant anomalies.

5. Performance Analysis

The time of operation is a crucial element in determining the usability of each algorithm, as it has direct impact on the feasibility of implementing it in real systems. It is especially if we need to deploy algorithms to devices with limited resources, like IoT devices. We are accustomed to almost instantaneous communication, where each millisecond has an impact. Aside from user experience, it also has serious security implications—judging by the time data encryption and decryption took, vital information like the key length and cipher used can be deduced. Lastly, when operations are performed on servers, the sudden increase in resource requirements due to a switch to post-quantum algorithms may be considered too costly. This resistance to change can leave critical systems vulnerable in the long run, as attackers eventually gain more powerful tools to break conventional encryption.

As seen in Table 2, the liboqs library details of each implemented post-quantum algorithm are presented. The claimed NIST level is a measurement of the computational power required to break an algorithm, ranging from 1—meaning the lowest degree of security—to 5—denoting the highest. Apart from the NIST level, it also presents the sizes of signatures, public, and private keys. It can be noted that while SPHINCS+ algorithms offer relatively small public- and private-key sizes, their signature lengths are noticeably larger than other algorithms. Additionally, each SPHINCS+ algorithm has two versions—with either an ‘s’ or ‘f’ suffix. The first version provides considerably smaller signature sizes at the cost of worse signing time. This distinction highlights important trade-offs in terms of the efficiency and usage of resources, emphasizing the need of choosing the algorithm based on application’s needs.

Table 2. Attributes of liboqs algorithms.

Algorithm	Claimed NIST Level	Public Key Size (Bytes)	Private Key Size (Bytes)	Signature Size (Bytes)
Dilithium2	2	1312	2528	2420
Dilithium3	3	1952	4000	3293
Dilithium5	5	2592	4864	4595
Falcon-512	1	897	1281	752
Falcon-1024	5	1793	2305	1462
Falcon-padded-512	1	897	1281	666
Falcon-padded-1024	5	1793	2305	1280
MAYO-1	1	1168	24	321
MAYO-2	1	5488	24	180
MAYO-3	3	2656	32	577
MAYO-5	5	5008	40	838
ML-DSA-44-ipd	2	1312	2560	2420
ML-DSA-65-ipd	3	1952	4032	3309
ML-DSA-87-ipd	5	2592	4896	4627
SPHINCS+-SHA2-128f-simple	1	32	64	17,088
SPHINCS+-SHA2-128s-simple	1	32	64	7856
SPHINCS+-SHA2-192f-simple	3	48	96	35,664
SPHINCS+-SHA2-192s-simple	3	48	96	16,224
SPHINCS+-SHA2-256f-simple	5	64	128	49,856
SPHINCS+-SHA2-256s-simple	5	64	128	29,792
SPHINCS+-SHAKE-128f-simple	1	32	64	17,088
SPHINCS+-SHAKE-128s-simple	1	32	64	7856
SPHINCS+-SHAKE-192f-simple	3	48	96	35,664
SPHINCS+-SHAKE-192s-simple	3	48	96	16,224
SPHINCS+-SHAKE-256f-simple	5	64	128	49,856
SPHINCS+-SHAKE-256s-simple	5	64	128	29,792

5.1. General Results

To initiate the analysis, the performance of the original library implementation was measured first. The results of this scenario are illustrated in Figure 2. Logarithmic scale has been applied to allow for an effective visualization of the performance differences. In the provided example, the MAYO-1 algorithm clearly achieved the best results in terms of speed. However, when cross-referenced with the previously provided NIST Table 2,

it becomes apparent that the MAYO-1 has a level of 1, denoting the lowest degree of security. Figure 3 focuses exclusively on the algorithms with the highest NIST security level—level 5. In this context, Dilithium5 presented performance comparable with the ML-DSA-87-ipd while surpassing the MAYO-5 execution times. Meanwhile, all SPHINCS+ implementations showcased significantly longer processing times. As expected, SPHINCS+ algorithms with the ‘f’ suffix yielded visibly better signing times than their counterparts with the ‘s’ suffix as a trade-off for longer signature size, leading to higher verification times. The presented results are similar to other performance benchmarks performed for post-quantum algorithms [24,25]. It is worth mentioning that the paper [24] considers only the performance analysis of the Python wrapper of the liboqs library. This paper presents an efficiency analysis of the NIST-standardized PQC algorithms in various environments: C, C++, Python, and Golang.

Figure 2. Performance analysis of C implementation for 1 KB file.

Figure 3. Performance analysis of C implementation for 1 KB file (only NIST level 5 algorithms).

Before examining performance with larger file sizes, it is important to highlight the different mechanisms used for algorithms of the SPHINCS+ family and Dilithium5. While the former uses the SHA2 function—an older algorithm for hashing—the latter implements the SHA3, which is newer and more secure but typically slower. This leads to varying performance outcomes across systems optimized for different hashing algorithms. Figures 4–6 represent the NIST level 5 algorithms for files of 1 MB, 50 MB, and 1 GB, respectively. As key generation times do not rely on file size and remain constant, they have been omitted from these graphs. The time for larger files will no longer be presented in the logarithmic scale for better visibility. It can be observed that for larger file sizes, algorithms Dilithium5, Falcon-1024, MAYO-5, and ML-DSA-97-ipd provided very similar results, with only noticeable differences in the SPHINCS+ algorithms. SPHINCS+-SHA2-256f offered noticeably better signing performance, and its disadvantage in verification time decreased as the file size increased.

The conclusion that can be drawn is that for relatively small file sizes, Dilithium5 indeed provides best performance across all aspects of the signing process when considering NIST security level 5 algorithms. While SPHINCS+-SHA256-f may appear more efficient with larger inputs, in practical scenarios, files as large as 1 GB are rarely signed directly. Instead, a hash of the message is computed and signed, greatly reducing the computational demand and bringing the input sizes back into a range where Dilithium5 excels.

Figure 4. Performance analysis of C implementation for 1 MB file (NIST level 5 algorithms).

Figure 5. Performance analysis of C implementation for 50 MB file (NIST level 5 algorithms).

Figure 6. Performance analysis of C implementation for 1 GB file (NIST level 5 algorithms).

5.2. Performance Across Programming Languages

To further evaluate the performance of the liboqs library and assess its feasibility across various applications, additional benchmarking tests were conducted with three programming languages. Figures 7–9 present the algorithms performance for C++, Golang, and Python respectively, for 1 KB file size.

Figure 7. Performance analysis of C++ implementation for 1 KB file (NIST level 5 algorithms).

Figure 8. Performance analysis of Golang implementation for 1 KB file (NIST level 5 algorithms).

Figure 9. Performance analysis of Python implementation for 1 KB file (NIST level 5 algorithms).

It can be noticed that, while certain algorithms had slight time variations between languages, the overall hierarchy remained the same. As Dilithium5 became the main focus of all the benchmarks, Figures 10 and 11 provide more detailed comparison of its performance across languages. In most cases, the overlapping mean errors bars indicate that the results are similar but prevent direct comparison. However the main takeaway is that for the 1 KB file size, the average execution time of the signing operation in Python was 127 μ s and 118 μ s for C++, resulting in an overhead of about 7.6%. As for key generation operation, the C++ average execution time was 64 μ s, while Python executed in 67 μ s, resulting in an overhead of approximately 4.6%. For the 1 GB file size (Figure 11), the

Python implementation appeared significantly worse, with an overhead approximately 14% for the signing and verification processes compared to the C++ wrapper.

Presented differences come from inherent language differences. Both C and C++ provide minimal overhead and are compiled directly to machine code. They offer manual memory management allowing for fine-tuned optimization. In comparison, Python is an interpreted language with automatic garbage collection, leading to noticeably worse performance. Another important factor in optimization is concurrency. While C and C++ offer advanced multithreading libraries, Python’s multithreading is hindered by a global interpreter lock (GIL) as a way of preventing race conditions.

The conclusion is that although each wrapper introduced overhead, it never exceeded 15%, with file sizes of 1 KB showing an overhead of no more than 5%. As the files are usually hashed first, this will be the most widely used scenario. Choosing a liboqs implementation for an application requires understanding its needs and whether an easier syntax and faster prototyping of the high-level language are worth a few % drop in performance. Applications that perform large amount of cryptographic operations each second and cannot allow for even slightest performance decrease will make the best use of original C implementation.

Figure 10. Performance analysis of Dilithium5 algorithm across languages for 1 KB file size.

Figure 11. Performance analysis of Dilithium5 algorithm across languages for 1 GB file size.

5.3. Performance Comparison with RSA Algorithm

This section aims to provide a comparative analysis between post-quantum and currently used asymmetric algorithms. It also addresses an essential question: Is the overhead introduced by post-quantum algorithms justified by the resilience against quantum-based attacks that they offer? The algorithm chosen for comparison is the well-known and popular RSA with a key length of 2048 bits and implemented by the OpenSSL library [26].

Figure 12 presents the benchmarking results for RSA and post-quantum algorithms on 1 KB data. Notably, RSA exhibited significantly lower performance in key generation and signing but outperformed other algorithms in verification, suggesting that post-quantum algorithms generally provide better overall performance in smaller-scale applications. However, Figure 13 shows a similar benchmark for a 1 GB file, where RSA significantly outperformed even the fastest post-quantum algorithms in terms of the signing and verification time—often by orders of magnitude. This disparity is largely due to RSA’s limitation on the message length, necessitating a hashing step that reduces the effective message size to a few hundred bytes, which can sometimes be parallelized. When this hashing approach was similarly applied to post-quantum algorithms, as shown in Figure 14, where RSA’s advantage narrowed significantly. It is worth mentioning that the performance of both RSA and most of the post-quantum algorithms in this scenario became so comparable that their error margins overlapped.

Presented measurements were performed on a general purpose computer, but by utilizing hardware tailored to specific algorithms needs, it is possible to achieve significantly better performance [27–29]. Using RISC-V System-on-Chips, Dilithium has been able to achieve up to 26x performance enhancements in comparison to software implementation [30].

Figure 12. Comparison between post-quantum algorithms and RSA for 1 KB file size.

Figure 13. Comparison between post-quantum algorithms and RSA for 1 GB file size.

Figure 14. Comparison between post-quantum algorithms with hashed input data and RSA for 1 GB file size.

6. Conclusions

This paper aims to benchmark various post-quantum signature algorithms across different programming languages and assess their performance relative to currently used asymmetric algorithms. The findings indicate that for the most widely used scenario—messages with size of 1 KB and smaller—post-quantum algorithms not only performed comparably to their classical counterparts but, in certain cases, even provided better performance. These findings indicate that these algorithms are strong candidates for implementation and the replacement of currently used standards to provide safety from quantum-based attacks. The research and development of these algorithms is still being continued, aiming to provide better performance and security. Future work might include benchmarking improved algorithms or even new post-quantum solutions. Additionally, future work could explore a performance comparison with algorithms other than RSA (e.g., elliptic curve cryptography) and evaluate the impact of signing files of varying sizes.

An important point to note is the significance of these findings for companies in various industries, particularly those dealing with sensitive data or requiring long-term data confidentiality. Organizations should begin planning for the integration of post-quantum algorithms into their systems, ensuring that the transition does not hinder their performance or adherence to standards. These algorithms can be implemented in software, offering flexibility and ease of deployment, or for more demanding applications, such as dedicated hardware solutions to achieve optimal performance.

Choosing both the Dilithium and SPHINCS+ families as prime candidates for signature scheme implementation has recently been announced by the NIST [5], with Dilithium standing out as a primary candidate. Consistent with official benchmarks from the liboqs library, performed tests show that Dilithium5 provides robust performance throughout the signing process while maintaining a competitive signature size. Although SPHINCS+ algorithms may offer slight performance advantages with larger file sizes, depending on system optimizations for specific hashing functions, the direct signing of large files is not a

common practice. Applications that prioritize minimal signature sizes will make the best use of Falcon algorithms, which outperform the SPHINCS+ family by orders of magnitude in this area. Regarding performance across languages, our results align with expectations: C and C++ implementations tend to perform slightly better than those in Go and Python. As highlighted, selecting an optimal environment is crucial for achieving the best performance tailored to specific application needs.

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